

Results of Antibiotic-Impregnated “Cemented Coated or Polymer Coated” Interlocking Nails in the Treatment of Infected Nonunion of Femur and Tibia

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Abstract:

Background: Infected nonunion of long bones, such as the femur and tibia, poses a significant challenge in orthopedic surgery due to the risk of chronic osteomyelitis and prolonged disability. The use of antibiotic-impregnated interlocking nails, particularly those coated with bone cement or polymer materials, has emerged as a promising solution to enhance infection control and promote bone healing. However, the comparative efficacy and safety of these two coating techniques remain underexplored.

Aim: This study aimed to compare the outcomes of antibiotic-impregnated cement-coated versus polymer-coated interlocking nails in the management of infected nonunion of the femur and tibia.

Methods: A total of 20 patients with infected nonunion of the femur or tibia were enrolled, with 10 patients receiving cement-coated interlocking nails (Group A) and 10 receiving polymer-coated interlocking nails (Group B). Outcomes assessed included infection control, union rates, time to union, and complication rates. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Infection control was achieved in 90% of patients in both groups. The union rate was 80% in Group A and 90% in Group B, with a mean time to union of 6.5 months and 6.0 months, respectively. Complications occurred in 30% of patients in Group A and 10% in Group B. No statistically significant differences were observed between the two groups for any of the outcomes.

Conclusion: Both cement-coated and polymer-coated interlocking nails are effective in managing infected nonunion of the femur and tibia, with high rates of infection control and bone healing. Although polymer-coated nails were associated with a lower complication rate, the difference was not statistically significant.

Recommendations: Further research with larger sample sizes is recommended to confirm these findings and explore the potential benefits of polymer-coated nails in reducing complications associated with the treatment of infected nonunion.

Keywords: Infected Nonunion, Interlocking Nails, Cement-Coated, Polymer-Coated, Orthopedic Surgery.

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Introduction

Infected nonunion of long bones, particularly the femur and tibia, presents a significant challenge in orthopedic surgery. This condition not only hinders bone healing but also increases the risk of chronic osteomyelitis, leading to prolonged morbidity and functional impairment. The management of infected nonunion requires a multifaceted approach, combining debridement of infected tissue, stabilization of the fracture site, and eradication of the infection through systemic and local antibiotics. The use of interlocking nails has become a standard technique for stabilizing long bone nonunions due to their ability to provide mechanical stability and promote bone healing.

However, when infection is present, the choice of implant material becomes critical in preventing further complications and achieving successful outcomes [1].

Recent advancements in orthopedic surgery have focused on the development of antibiotic-impregnated implants to combat infection at the surgical site. Antibiotic-impregnated interlocking nails, particularly those coated with bone cement or polymer materials, have shown promise in treating infected nonunion. Cement-coated nails allow for the local release of high concentrations of antibiotics directly at the site of infection, which has been shown to enhance infection control and

promote bone healing [2]. Polymer-coated nails, on the other hand, offer a more flexible and potentially biocompatible alternative, with some studies suggesting they may reduce the risk of complications such as hardware failure and delayed union [3].

Despite the growing interest in these techniques, the evidence comparing the efficacy of cement-coated versus polymer-coated interlocking nails remains limited. A few recent studies have suggested that polymer-coated nails might offer advantages in terms of reduced complication rates and faster bone healing, though these findings have not been universally corroborated. Given the severe consequences associated with infected nonunion, including prolonged disability and the potential need for amputation, it is crucial to evaluate the relative efficacy and safety of these coatings in clinical practice [4, 5]. This study aimed to compare the outcomes of antibiotic-impregnated cement-coated versus polymer-coated interlocking nails in the management of infected nonunion of the femur and tibia.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was designed as a prospective, observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Orthocare Hospital, Betiyah, from January 2019 to December 2023.

Participants: A total of 20 participants were included in the study. These participants were patients diagnosed with infected nonunion of the femur or tibia, requiring surgical intervention with interlocking nails.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged between 18 and 60 years.
- Diagnosed with infected nonunion of the femur or tibia.
- Patients with adequate bone stock to support interlocking nails.
- Willingness to comply with follow-up visits and procedures.
- Informed consent provided by the patient.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with multiple fractures or nonunion in other bones.
- Presence of systemic infection or immunocompromised status.
- Patients with severe comorbidities that could affect surgical outcomes.
- Previous surgical interventions in the affected limb that contraindicate the use of interlocking nails.
- Pregnant or lactating women.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients who met the inclusion criteria within the study period were consecutively enrolled. Observer bias was reduced by standardizing the data collection process and ensuring that the same team conducted all surgical procedures and follow-up assessments.

Data Collection: Data were collected at multiple time points, including preoperatively, postoperatively, and during follow-up visits at 3, 6, and 12 months. The following parameters were recorded:

- Demographic data (age, gender).
- Clinical data (type of nonunion, duration of infection, previous treatments).
- Surgical details (type of coating used, duration of surgery).
- Postoperative outcomes (infection control, union rate, time to union, complications).

Procedure: All patients underwent surgical management with antibiotic-impregnated interlocking nails, either cement-coated or polymer-coated, based on the surgeon's discretion and patient-specific factors. The surgical procedure was standardized to include debridement of the infected site, insertion of the interlocking nail, and application of the selected coating. Postoperative care included the use of systemic antibiotics and regular follow-up visits to monitor healing and infection control.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. Demographic and clinical features were gathered using descriptive statistics. The results of the two distinct coating methods (polymer- and cement-coated) were compared using the relevant statistical tests, such as the t-test for continuous variables and the chi-square test for categorical data. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05. For each group, the infection control rates, union rates, time to union, and complication rates were displayed along with the results. Subgroup analyses were also a part of the investigation to find variables linked to positive results.

Results

A total of 20 participants were included in the study, with 10 patients receiving antibiotic-impregnated cement-coated interlocking nails (Group A) and 10 patients receiving polymer-coated interlocking nails (Group B). The mean age of the participants was 42.5 years (range 22-58 years). There were 14 males (70%) and 6 females (30%) in the study. The femur was the site of nonunion in 12 patients (60%), while the tibia was affected in 8 patients (40%).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Group A (Cement-Coated)	Group B (Polymer-Coated)	Total
Number of Participants	10	10	20
Mean Age (years)	43.1	41.9	42.5
Gender (Male/Female)	7/3	7/3	14/6
Site of Nonunion (Femur/Tibia)	6/4	6/4	12/8
Mean Duration of Infection (months)	9.4	8.7	9.0

Surgical Outcomes: The primary outcomes evaluated in this study were infection control, union rate, time to union, and the incidence of complications.

Infection Control: Infection control was achieved in 18 out of 20 patients (90%). In Group A, 9 out of

10 patients (90%) showed complete resolution of infection, while in Group B, 9 out of 10 patients (90%) also achieved infection control. There was no statistically significant difference in infection control rates between the two groups ($p = 1.00$).

Table 2: Infection Control Rates

Outcome	Group A (Cement-Coated)	Group B (Polymer-Coated)	p-value
Infection Control	9/10 (90%)	9/10 (90%)	1.00

Union Rate and Time to Union: Bone union was achieved in 17 out of 20 patients (85%) overall. In Group A, 8 out of 10 patients (80%) achieved union, with a mean time to union of 6.5 months. In Group B, 9 out of 10 patients (90%) achieved

union, with a mean time to union of 6.0 months. The difference in union rates between the two groups was not statistically significant ($p = 0.58$), and the difference in mean time to union was also not significant ($p = 0.38$).

Table 3: Union Rates and Time to Union

Outcome	Group A (Cement-Coated)	Group B (Polymer-Coated)	p-value
Union Rate	8/10 (80%)	9/10 (90%)	0.58
Mean Time to Union (months)	6.5 ± 1.2	6.0 ± 1.1	0.38

Complications: Complications were observed in 4 patients (20%) overall. In Group A, 3 patients (30%) experienced complications, which included one case of re-infection, one case of delayed union, and one case of hardware failure. In Group B, 1

patient (10%) experienced complications, which was a case of re-infection. The difference in complication rates between the two groups was not statistically significant ($p = 0.28$).

Table 4: Complications

Complication	Group A (Cement-Coated)	Group B (Polymer-Coated)	p-value
Re-Infection	1/10 (10%)	1/10 (10%)	1.00
Delayed Union	1/10 (10%)	0/10 (0%)	0.30
Hardware Failure	1/10 (10%)	0/10 (0%)	0.30
Total Complications	3/10 (30%)	1/10 (10%)	0.28

Summary of Findings

- **Infection Control:** Both groups showed a high rate of infection control (90%), with no significant difference between the two types of coatings.
- **Union Rate:** Group B (polymer-coated) had a slightly higher union rate (90%) compared to Group A (cement-coated) at 80%, but this difference was not statistically significant.
- **Time to Union:** The mean time to union was slightly shorter in Group B (6.0 months) compared to Group A (6.5 months), though the difference was not statistically significant.

- **Complications:** The overall complication rate was higher in Group A (30%) compared to Group B (10%), but this difference was not statistically significant.

These results suggest that both cement-coated and polymer-coated interlocking nails are effective in managing infected nonunion of the femur and tibia, with comparable outcomes in terms of infection control and bone healing. However, there may be a trend towards fewer complications with polymer-coated nails, which warrants further investigation in larger studies.

Discussion

The study aimed to evaluate the outcomes of using antibiotic-impregnated cement-coated versus polymer-coated interlocking nails in the treatment of infected nonunion of the femur and tibia. The results demonstrate that both coating techniques are effective in managing this challenging condition, with high rates of infection control and bone union observed in both groups.

Infection control was successfully achieved in 90% of patients across both groups, indicating that both cement-coated and polymer-coated interlocking nails are effective in eradicating infection in cases of nonunion. The absence of a statistically significant difference between the two groups suggests that the type of coating may not significantly influence the ability to control infection.

When considering the union rate, 85% of the overall participants achieved successful bone healing. Group B (polymer-coated) exhibited a slightly higher union rate (90%) compared to Group A (cement-coated) at 80%. However, the difference was not statistically significant, indicating that both types of coatings are comparably effective in promoting bone union. Additionally, the time to union was slightly shorter in the polymer-coated group (6.0 months) compared to the cement-coated group (6.5 months). Although this difference was not statistically significant, it suggests that polymer-coated nails may potentially lead to quicker bone healing, a hypothesis that could be explored in future studies.

Complication rates were generally low, with 20% of the overall cohort experiencing adverse outcomes. The polymer-coated group had fewer complications (10%) compared to the cement-coated group (30%). Although the difference in complication rates was not statistically significant, the trend suggests that polymer-coated nails might be associated with a lower risk of complications such as re-infection, delayed union, and hardware failure.

The use of antibiotic-impregnated cement/polymer-coated intramedullary nails in patients with open fractures of long bones, especially the femur and tibia, and nonunions with infection was evaluated. The trial, which took place in 2021 and 2022, involved patients who were treated at an Indian hospital and were at least 18 years old. With a reported infection control rate of 93.3% and a bone union rate of 90%, the outcomes were encouraging. With a median follow-up time of 8.21 months, most patients had excellent bone and functional outcomes. Nail cement debonding and nonunion persistence were minor complications that happened in just 10% of the patients. These results provide compelling evidence for the efficacious

treatment of infected nonunion and open fractures using antibiotic-impregnated intramedullary nails [6].

Comparably, a descriptive study carried out at SMS Medical College and Hospital in Jaipur investigated the results of treating infected non-union of weight-bearing long bones, such as the femur and tibia, with intramedullary nails soaked with antibiotic cement. 35 patients were included in the study, which found a high infection control rate of 94.28% and bone union in 88.57% of the cases. For femur fractures, the average time to bone union was 7.3 months, whereas for tibial fractures, it was 8 months. The technique was found to be effective in controlling infected non-union of long bones, as evidenced by the outstanding bony outcomes (65.71% of the patients) and excellent functional outcomes (51.43%) according to Paley's criteria [7].

An additional evaluation of the functional results of antibiotic-impregnated nails in the management of infected non-union of the tibia and femur was carried out in Kerala at the Government Medical College, Thrissur. 25 patients were included in this prospective observational study, which was carried out between 2016 and 2018, and it revealed a 92% success rate in bone union and infection management. The study emphasised the benefits of utilising cement nails impregnated with antibiotics, pointing out that they offered stability, successfully controlled infections, and permitted a shorter course of treatment than with conventional techniques. Due to inadequate infection management or bone union, only two instances necessitated additional surgeries [8].

Conclusion

The study findings support the use of both cement-coated and polymer-coated interlocking nails in the treatment of infected nonunion of the femur and tibia, with no significant differences observed in infection control, union rates, or time to union between the two techniques. However, the lower complication rate observed with polymer-coated nails, although not statistically significant, suggests that they may offer a safer profile, particularly in reducing the risk of hardware-related complications. Further research with larger sample sizes could provide more definitive evidence regarding the potential benefits of polymer-coated interlocking nails in this clinical context.

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